

GRAPHENE-CARBON BLACK- SILICONE RUBBER COMPOSITE FILMS WITH LOW TEMPERATURE-COEFFICIENTS OF RESISTANCE FOR LARGE STRAIN SENSORS

Agee Susan Kurian, Velram Balaji Mohan and Debes Bhattacharyya*

Centre for Advanced Composite Materials, Department of Mechanical Engineering, The University of Auckland, 314 Khyber Pass Road, Newmarket, Auckland, New Zealand, 1142.

Corresponding author*: d.bhattacharyya@auckland.ac.nz

Keywords: Low Temperature-coefficient, Large Strain Sensor, Sandwich, Gauge Factor, Piezoresistivity

ABSTRACT

Composite materials with carbonaceous fillers in a polymer matrix have gained remarkable academic and industrial attention due to their characteristic properties like design flexibility, low cost, corrosion resistance and lightweight. In this work, we fabricated graphene nanoplatelets (G)-carbon black (CB)-silicone rubber (SR) hybrid films by solution casting. The most attractive characteristic of the composite thin films is that they can be engineered to obtain a low temperature-coefficients of resistance (TCR). G/SR films exhibited a positive temperature coefficients of resistance (PTC) while CB/SR films exhibited a negative temperature coefficients of resistance (NTC). The synergistic effect of graphene and carbon black can accomplish improved characteristics which the individual filler cannot due to the development of correlated networks between them. A large strain sensor was fabricated with G-CB-SR composite film embedded within the SR substrates, which had good electromechanical properties and had no requirement for a resistance compensating circuit due to its low TCR.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conductive polymer composites (CPC) [1] have attracted significant attention due to their distinct properties like low cost, ease of manufacturing and corrosion resistance and many more. But most of the CPC are rigid and brittle which restrict their usage in many challenging applications such as wearable sensors [2], robotics and human motion detectors. The rapid advances and developments of the electronic industries have been based on electronic components having greater precision and consistency. To accomplish effective and steady functioning, components with stability are essential. One of the challenges in the electronic industry is heat dissipation due to electronic devices. Self-heating of the electronic devices hampers the performance of the electronic devices. For many electronic device applications, composites with a low-temperature coefficients of resistance (TCR) are particularly desirable because composites with negative temperature coefficients of resistance (NTC) can produce heat in the circuit. To address this issue, materials have been developed with low TCR, which are promising candidates in the manufacturing of highly accurate electronic integrated circuits and sensor applications for efficient functioning. In this paper, we report a hybrid composite flexible and stretchable film [3] with two conductive fillers, graphene nanoplatelets (G) and carbon black (CB) of different geometry and properties, and explore the possibility to obtain composites with multifunctional properties.

A combination of two or more fillers with varying structural and intrinsic characteristics have been used to modify the properties single filler/polymer system, which has proved that composites with enhanced characteristics can be materialized. Researches have been done on hybrid composites with various combinations being examined such as G with single-walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT) [4, 5],

G with multiwalled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) [6, 7], G with CB [8, 9] and MWCNT with CB [10, 11]. Higher thermal conductivity values were reported for SWCNT-G/epoxy composites [4] at a specific filler loading level than SWCNT/epoxy and G/epoxy composites. Electrodes for supercapacitors were developed by G-CB composites [9] with improved electrochemical properties than G and CB. G-MWCNT/epoxy composites [6] were reported with better mechanical properties than G/epoxy and MWCNT/epoxy composites. Here, we opted CB with graphene, which has good electrical conductivity and low price to fabricate a hybrid film with graphene.

The resistance of an ideal strain sensor changes only with strain. However, in ordinary cases, the resistance of the sensing element varies with temperature. This can cause error in strain measurements. So usually a temperature compensating circuit is required to obtain accurate strain measurement. This paper reports the fabrication of a large strain sensor which has stability against time and temperature and has no requirement for a resistance compensating circuit due to its low TCR of the sensing element.

2. METHOD OF PREPARATION

Here we used a simple, low-cost solution casting method. G and CB were dispersed in toluene using sonication and magnetic stirring. Then the polymer, silicone rubber (SR) is added to it and mixed well with a magnetic stirrer. It is then poured onto a cured SR substrate in an acrylic mould and cured well by keeping in an oven at 80°C for 1 hour and 100°C for 2 hours. The second layer of SR is poured over it to protect the film. Fig. 1 shows the dimensions of a wearable sensor made with this film. Fig. 2 shows the sample prepared, its excellent stretchability and flexibility. Composites for the rheological studies were prepared without using the solvent.

Fig. 1 Dimensions of the sensor

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Introduction of CBs into the Gs prevents the agglomeration of the Gs because CBs deposit on the edge planes of the Gs. Better dispersion of the fillers occurs due to the interactions of the fillers and the SR. CBs increase the space between the Gs, inhibiting aggregation of the Gs, which enables the diffusion of the SR polymer chains resulting in greater electromechanical properties. Due to the high conductivity of Gs, it can be concluded that the voltage drop across the Gs is negligible when compared to the voltage drop across the G-SR junctions. CPC typically demonstrate an increase in resistance known as PTC or decrease in resistance known as NTC. One of the main reason for the PTC in polymer composites is due to the thermal expansion of the polymers between the fillers. When G/SR composite is heated, the SR layer between the Gs expands, which increases the distance between the adjacent Gs, thereby hindering the quantum mechanical tunnelling of electrons.

Fig. 2 (a) as prepared sample (b) 300% stretching (c) twisting

Fig. 3 shows the resistance-temperature (R-T) characteristics of the composites. It is evident from Fig. 3(a) that the G/SR composites displayed a PTC [3, 12] of resistance while CB/SR composites showed a NTC [13] of resistance. Unlike G/SR composites, quantum mechanical tunnelling plays a vital role in G-CB-SR composites. The PTC of G/polymer [14, 15] composites is reported already. The change in resistance of composites from 293 K to 393 K was studied. G/SR composites with less G wt. % shows a higher rate of increase in resistance as in Fig. 3(b) due to the more significant amount of the SR. Unlike G/SR composites, CB/SR composites showed NTC as in Fig. 3(a). Due to the difference in morphology and intrinsic properties, there is a difference in the conductive networks in the G/SR and CB/SR composites. When CB/SR composites are heated, the electrons get more energy to cross the tunnel junctions and hence shows NTC.

An explanation of the phenomenon observed in the G-CB-SR composites depends on the concentration of the fillers G and CB. The mechanism of resistance variation on temperature variation of the hybrid film revealed that the interaction between G and CB are responsible for the tunable resistance to temperature variation. In G-CB-SR composites with equal wt. % of G and CB, a synergy of the fillers causes a balanced effect in which in temperature remain almost unaffected as in Fig. 3(b). Hence, G-CB-SR composite sensors need no compensation for resistance drift over the temperature in real life applications.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3 R –T plot of composites (a) G/SR with higher graphene wt. %, CB/SR (b) G/SR with low graphene wt. %, G-CB-SR

Temperature coefficient of resistance can be calculated using the formula

$$R = R_{\text{ref}} [1 + \alpha (T - T_{\text{ref}})]$$

where R is the resistance at temperature T , R_{ref} is the resistance at temperature T_{ref} (normally 20°C) and α is the temperature coefficient of resistance.

Sample composition	Mean α (/°C)
G 4.17 wt. %	1.34×10^{-2}
G 3.85 wt. %	2.12×10^{-2}
G 3.57 wt. %	5.38×10^{-2}
G 2.08 wt. % CB 0.69 wt. %	7.21×10^{-3}
G 0.69 wt. % CB 2.08 wt. %	-5.3×10^{-3}
G 1.39 wt. % CB 1.39 wt. %	5.39×10^{-4}

Table 1: Temperature coefficient of resistance of the composites

Generally, metals show PTC while semiconductors exhibit a NTC. CPC exhibit PTC or NTC depending on the fillers and the nature of the conductive network. The TCR of the various composites examined are shown in Table 1. It is observed that G/SR composites with 4.17 wt. % of G exhibits PTC with a mean TCR of $1.34 \times 10^{-2}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. The composites show an increasing TCR value with increasing polymer content. This could be due to the fact that, with more polymer content, polymer layer between the fillers becomes thicker, which inhibits the possibilities of quantum mechanical tunnelling between the fillers resulting increase resistance. However, the addition of CBs has a significant influence on TCR, and the TCR starts decreasing as shown in Table 1. The G-CB-SR composites with 0.69 wt.% of CB, the mean TCR reaches a value of $7.21 \times 10^{-3}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. Increasing the CBs further, decreases the TCR and with 2.08 wt. %, PTC changes to NTC attaining a value of -5.3×10^{-3}

$^3/^{\circ}\text{C}$. But composite with equal wt. % of G and CB show a low TCR with a value reaching $5.39 \times 10^{-4}/^{\circ}\text{C}$.

To design G-CB-SR composite film as a wearable sensor, the film is sandwiched between two SR substrates. A sensor with dimensions as in Fig.1 is fabricated by pasting adhesive tapes on SR substrates so that a narrow film of size $70 \text{ mm} \times 6 \text{ mm}$ is constructed to avoid the necking effect of the film on stretching. The second layer of SR poured cures and produces a seamless and robust bond with the cured SR substrate layer thereby protecting the conductive trace completely and preventing delamination of the film making it suitable for long term use.

The electromechanical behaviour of the composites was studied, and it is shown in Fig. 4. The sensor showed piezoresistivity, excellent stretchability, and good sensor characteristics like low hysteresis and gauge factor suitable for a large strain wearable sensor. The durability of the strain sensor was assessed, and the G-CB-SR strain sensor was subjected to multiple cycles of repeated stretching and relaxation from a strain 0% to 100% with a strain rate of 1 mm s^{-1} . Fig. 5 shows the durable performance of the strain sensor. Moreover, the sensor does not require a resistance compensating circuit due to its low TCR.

Fig. 4 Normalised resistance- strain curve of G-CB-SR composite

Fig. 5 Long-term stability of a strain sensor G-CB-SR sensor for 500 cycles

G-CB-SR composite films were prepared with varying CB wt. % and the rheological studies were done using Dynamic Mechanical Analyser. It was revealed that the inclusion of CB has modified the glass transition temperature (T_g) and the storage modulus of the SR. The pristine SR showed a glass transition temperature (T_g) at -110°C while the G-CB-SR composite film showed a lowering tendency of the T_g which could be due to the synergistic effect of the fillers acting as a plasticiser [16] modifying the molecular motions of the amorphous phase of SR. However, further studies are required

to fully comprehend this phenomena. Fig. 6(a) and 6(b) show the SEM images of the fillers G and CB, respectively. Fig. 6(c) and Fig. 6(d) show the microstructure of the G/SR composites and G-CB-SR composites, respectively.

Fig. 6 SEM images of (a) G particles (b) CB particles (c) G/SR composites (d) G-CB-SR composites

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study we prepared G/SR, CB/SR and G-CB-SR composite films by a simple, solution casting method. The resistance of G/SR and CB/SR film were found to be sensitive to temperature. It was observed that synergistic effect of G and CB could bring about better functionalities that individual filler could not due to the formation of interconnected networks. A large strain sensor was fabricated with G-CB-SR film which showed good electromechanical characteristics. The low TCR of G-CB-SR composites makes them suitable for the fabrication of standard resistors in high-temperature applications. Besides they can be used for applications which requires reliable temperature control such as heating and functional sensor applications which require thermal stability of the properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment, New Zealand (Grant No: 3706657). The authors are grateful to the CACM technicians for their technical support.

REFERENCES

1. Mohan, V.B., B.J. Krebs, and D. Bhattacharyya, *Development of novel highly conductive 3D printable hybrid polymer-graphene composites*. Materials Today Communications, 2018. **17**: p. 554-561.
2. Kurian, A.S., et al., *Printing of CNT/silicone rubber for a wearable flexible stretch sensor*. 2016. **9798**: p. 97980K.
3. Kurian, A.S., V.B. Mohan, and D. Bhattacharyya, *Embedded large strain sensors with graphene-carbon black-silicone rubber composites*. Sensors and Actuators A: Physical, 2018. **282**: p. 206-214.
4. Yu, A., et al., *Enhanced thermal conductivity in a hybrid graphite nanoplatelet-carbon nanotube filler for epoxy composites*. Advanced Materials, 2008. **20**(24): p. 4740-4744.
5. Huang, C.-L., et al., *The effect of geometric factor of carbon nanofillers on the electrical conductivity and electromagnetic interference shielding properties of poly (trimethylene terephthalate) composites: a comparative study*. Journal of Materials Science, 2017. **52**(5): p. 2560-2580.
6. Chatterjee, S., et al., *Size and synergy effects of nanofiller hybrids including graphene nanoplatelets and carbon nanotubes in mechanical properties of epoxy composites*. Carbon, 2012. **50**(15): p. 5380-5386.
7. Lin, J.H., et al., *Improvement in Mechanical Properties and Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Effectiveness of PVA - Based Composites: Synergistic Effect Between Graphene Nano - Sheets and Multi - Walled Carbon Nanotubes*. Macromolecular Materials and Engineering, 2016. **301**(2): p. 199-211.
8. Wang, Y., et al., *Graphene/carbon black hybrid film for flexible and high rate performance supercapacitor*. Journal of Power Sources, 2014. **271**: p. 269-277.
9. Yan, J., et al., *Electrochemical properties of graphene nanosheet/carbon black composites as electrodes for supercapacitors*. Carbon, 2010. **48**(6): p. 1731-1737.
10. Dong, B., et al., *Effects of hybrid filler networks of carbon nanotubes and carbon black on fracture resistance of styrene - butadiene rubber composites*. Polymer Engineering & Science, 2016. **56**(12): p. 1425-1431.
11. Ismail, H., A. Ramly, and N. Othman, *The effect of carbon black/multiwall carbon nanotube hybrid fillers on the properties of natural rubber nanocomposites*. Polymer-Plastics Technology and Engineering, 2011. **50**(7): p. 660-666.
12. He, L. and S.-C. Tjong, *Electrical behavior and positive temperature coefficient effect of graphene/polyvinylidene fluoride composites containing silver nanowires*. Nanoscale research letters, 2014. **9**(1): p. 375.
13. Liu, X., et al. *Study on NTC Electrical Behavior of Carbon Black/PVC Composite*. in *2nd International Conference on Electronic & Mechanical Engineering and Information Technology*. 2012. Atlantis Press.

14. Mohsin, K., et al., *Temperature Sensitivity of Electrical Resistivity of Graphene/Copper Hybrid Nano Ribbon Interconnect: A First Principle Study*. ECS Journal of Solid State Science and Technology, 2017. **6**(4): p. P119-P124.
15. Tian, M., et al., *Temperature-dependent electrical properties of graphene nanoplatelets film dropped on flexible substrates*. Journal of Materials Research, 2014. **29**(11): p. 1288-1294.
16. Zhiltsov, A., et al., *Polylactide and hybrid silicasol nanoparticle-based composites*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 2015. **132**(17).